

Electrochemical reduction of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-3-hydroxytriazene and its copper complex

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Abstract : 3-Methyl-1-phenyl-3-hydroxytriazene (MPHT) and its Cu complex were synthesized, purified and characterized by spectral techniques. The electrochemical reduction of MPHT was studied in aqueous methanolic solution containing BR buffer using DC-polarography and cyclic voltammetry. The DC-polarogram and cyclic voltammograms displayed only one reduction wave. The kinetic parameters have been evaluated. The cyclic voltammetric data reveals that the reduction is irreversible and follows an EC mechanism involving transfer of six electrons. Constant current electrolysis of MPHT was carried out using stainless steel electrode. The products of electro-reduction were isolated, purified and then characterized by spectroscopic methods. The proposed mechanism is given for electro-reduction of MPHT in acidic, aqueous and alkaline medium. The voltammetric studies of Cu complex of MPHT at Pt electrode in CH_2Cl_2 shows one electron quasi-reversible electrode process.

Keywords : Electrochemical reduction, 3-methyl-1-phenyl-3-hydroxytriazene, cyclic voltammetry, glassy carbon electrode, constant current electrolysis.

Introduction

The electrochemical behaviour of compounds containing nitrogen and oxygen donor atoms has attracted great interest in recent years. A perusal of literature reveals potential applications of hydroxytriazenes in the field of radical polymerization¹, complexometric², spectrophotometric determinations³⁻⁶, textile⁷ and pharmaceutical industries⁸ etc. Therefore the electrochemical investigation of hydroxytriazenes and their metal complexes shed light on their various uses.

The present communication deals with the synthesis, spectral and electrochemical studies of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-3-hydroxytriazene (MPHT) and its Cu complex. The electrochemical reduction of MPHT has been studied at DME by polarography and at glassy carbon, Pt electrode by cyclic voltammetry in different solvents. MPHT was subjected to constant current electrolysis using stainless steel as a cathodic material. Stainless steel electrode (SS-316), an economically viable electrode, has been used successfully in our laboratory^{9,10}.

Experimental

Analytical grade reagents were used in the synthesis

of MPHT and its Cu complex and also to prepare Britton-Robinson (BR) series buffer solutions, NaClO_4 and tetraethyl ammonium perchlorate solution as supporting electrolyte in voltammetric studies.

Synthesis of MPHT :

MPHT was synthesized by the reaction of methyl hydroxylamine and benzene diazonium chloride at 0–5 °C in 1 : 1 molar proportion in sodium acetate buffer (pH 5.00) as reported in the literature¹¹. It was recrystallized using aqueous-alcoholic mixture to yield cream needle shaped crystals (m.p. 69 °C). Further its purity was also confirmed by thin layer chromatography, yield 5.9 g (Found : C, 55.02; H, 4.89; N, 27.70. Calcd. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{O}$: C, 55.62; H, 5.96; N, 27.81%).

Synthesis of complex :

Copper complex of MPHT was synthesized by drop wise addition of hot alcoholic solution of ligand to the aqueous solution of cupric chloride with metal ligand ratio 1 : 2 with constant stirring. The solid was recrystallized by acetone to yield brown needle shaped crystals, yield 46% (Found : C, 46.91; H, 5.49; N, 22.19. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{Cu}$: C, 46.21, H, 4.40, N, 23.10%).

Physical measurements :

The spectral studies of MPHT were carried out for its characterization using FTIR spectrophotometer (Model 8400S, Shimadzu) and 300.4 MHz FT NMR spectrometer (Model Jeol AL 300). The infrared spectrum was recorded in KBr wafer phase while ^1H NMR and ^{13}C spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 using TMS as an internal standard. The DC-polarogram was obtained using Elico CL 358 DC polarographic analyser employing dropping mercury as working electrode and saturated calomel as reference electrode. All cyclic voltammograms of MPHT were recorded on a Basic Electrochemistry System (Model ECDA 001) using 3-electrode cell assembly with 1 mm diameter glassy carbon as working electrode, Ag/AgCl as reference electrode and Pt wire as counter electrode in aqueous methanolic medium containing sodium perchlorate as supporting electrolyte to maintain the ionic strength of the solution. BR series buffer solutions were used to maintain the pH of the solutions at 5.0, 7.0 and 9.0. The digital pH meter Model 101E (Electronics India) was used to measure the pH of solution. The experiments were performed at various scan rates using three different concentrations (0.16, 0.24 and 0.32 mM) of MPHT at room temperature 25 ± 0.5 °C. Cyclic voltammograms of MPHT and its Cu complex were also recorded in dichloromethane at Pt electrode using tetraethyl ammonium perchlorate as supporting electrolyte. The solutions were deoxygenated by purging high purity N_2 gas for at least 15 min before taking measurement.

Controlled current electrolysis (0.5 amp. for 24 h) of MPHT (0.01 M) containing 1 M CH_3COONa was carried out in aqueous methanolic solution (1 : 1) using stainless steel (SS-316) electrode (4 cm \times 4 cm) as cathode as well as anode respectively. The products obtained after repeated extraction and purification were then subjected to spectral studies for their characterization.

Results and discussion*IR and NMR spectra :*

Spectroscopic techniques were used to elucidate the structure of MPHT. The IR spectrum of MPHT displays absorption bands at 3200 ($\nu_{\text{O-H}}$), 1310 ($\delta_{\text{O-H}}$), 1600, 1500, 1440 ($\nu_{\text{C=C}}$ in-plane skeletal vibrations), 1415 ($\nu_{\text{N=N}}$), 985 ($\nu_{\text{N-O}}$), 1170, 1080 ($\delta_{\text{C-H}}$ in-plane), 1030 and 690 cm^{-1} ($\delta_{\text{C-H}}$ out-of-plane).

The ^1H NMR spectrum of MPHT shows signals at δ 3.90 methyl protons, δ 6.99 aryl protons and at δ 10.12

OH proton. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of MPHT exhibits absorption signals at δ 139.78 quaternary carbon (C^1), δ 129.44 $\text{C}^2=\text{C}^6$, 122.22 $\text{C}^3=\text{C}^5$, 114.28 C^4 of the aromatic ring while signal at δ 49.97 is assigned due to methyl carbon (C^7).

The disappearance of absorption band at 3200 cm^{-1} ($\nu(\text{O-H})$) in the IR spectrum of its Cu complex indicates the coordination of OH group to the metal ion while $\text{N}=\text{N}$ stretching band is shifted to a lower frequency (1320 cm^{-1}) in the complex indicating the coordination of ligand to metal ion via both N and O atom. The IR bands appearing at 440 and 500–520 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu(\text{M-O})$ and $\nu(\text{M-N})$ vibrations. In the ^1H NMR spectrum of the Cu complex, the OH proton signal was found to be absent, confirming deprotonation and its subsequent involvement in coordination.

Polarographic behaviour :

The DC-polarogram of 0.16 mM MPHT was recorded in aqueous methanolic solution using NaClO_4 as supporting electrolyte containing BR series buffer maintaining the pH of solution 5. The recorded polarogram displayed only single reduction wave.

Cyclic voltammetry :

The cyclic voltammograms of 0.16 mM aqueous methanolic solution of MPHT at the glassy carbon electrode (GCE) were recorded within the potential window of 600 to -1700 mV. Figs. 1–3 shows the cyclic voltammograms of MPHT at different scan rates 50, 100, 300, 400, 500 mV/s. In all the cases a single cathodic peak was observed. The anodic half cycle does not show any peak indicating that the concerned electro reduction is irreversible. The voltammetric data^{12–14} for reduction of MPHT to its products are given in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of 0.16 mM MPHT in aqueous methanolic medium containing BR buffer (pH 5.0).

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of 0.16 mM MPHT in aqueous methanolic medium containing BR buffer (pH 7).

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of 0.16 mM MPHT in aqueous methanolic medium containing BR buffer (pH 9.0).

Table 1. Effect of sweep rate on voltammetric parameters of 0.16 mM MPHT in aqueous methanolic solution containing BR buffer at pH (1) 5.0, (2) 7.0, (3) 9.0

pH	v (mV/s)	E_p (mV)	$E_{p1/2}$ (mV)	I_p (mA)	$I_p/v^{1/2}$	αn
5.0	50	-1134	-1013	110	16.83	0.0003942
	100	-1166	-1046	171	17.1	0.0003975
	300	-1227	-1097	318	18.38	0.000367
	400	-1232	-1099	355	18.4	0.0003587
	500	-1258	-1110	388	18.82	0.0003223
7.0	50	-1302	-1181	87	12.3	0.0003942
	100	-1318	-1189	128	12.8	0.0003698
	300	-1441	-1311	222	12.83	0.000367
	400	-1461	-1339	273	13.65	0.000391
	500	-1477	-1350	341	15.25	0.0003756
9.0	50	-1446	-1309	121	17.11	0.0003482
	100	-1466	-1326	175	17.5	0.0003407
	300	-1569	-1450	303	17.34	0.0004009
	400	-1579	-1478	368	18.4	0.00047
	500	-1591	-1496	443	19.8	0.0005022

Effect of pH :

Effect of pH on the peak potential and peak current was studied using 0.16 mM MPHT in aqueous methanolic solution using Britton-Robinson buffer at three different pH values 5.0, 7.0 and 9.0. The cathodic peak potential E_{pc} increases from -1134 to -1591 mV with increase in pH, suggesting that the reduction becomes difficult at higher pH values (Figs. 1-3).

Effect of concentration :

The effect of concentration of MPHT was studied in aqueous methanolic medium using Britton-Robinson buffer and NaClO₄ as supporting electrolyte. As the concentration of MPHT was varied from 0.16 to 0.32 mM, the cathodic current I_{pc} values obtained were found to increase linearly with increase in concentration (Table 2). The linear plot of I_{pc} versus concentration of MPHT indicates that electrode process was diffusion controlled¹⁵. It was also observed that the peak potential E_{pc} and half peak potential $E_{pc/2}$ were shifted towards more negative potential values with increase in concentration. The values of standard rate constant (k_0) indicate the irreversibility of electrode process (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of concentration of MPHT on cyclic voltammetric parameters for the reduction at GCE in aqueous alcoholic medium containing Britton-Robinson buffer of pH 9.0

Conc. of MPHT (mM)	E_{pc} (mV)	I_{pc} (μ A)	Diffusion coefficient ($D_0 \times 10^{-3}$ cm ² s ⁻¹)	Standard rate constant ($k_0 \times 10^{-22}$ cm s ⁻¹)
0.16	-1569	303	9.81	0.691
0.24	-1671	342	8.49	3.09
0.32	-1825	406	8.19	5.09

Effect of scan rate :

The concentration of MPHT was kept constant at 0.16 mM in aqueous methanolic medium. The scan rate was varied from 50 to 500 mV/s. The reduction peak potentials were found to shift linearly to their more negative values with increase in the scan rate as shown in Fig. 4. It indicates the irreversible nature of the electrode process. The small influence on current function of scan rate i.e. $I_{pc}/v^{1/2}$ reveals no significant adsorption at the electrode and thus the electrochemical reaction is followed by a chemical reaction (Fig. 5). The peak current was found to increase linearly with square root of scan rate (Fig. 6) which confirms the diffusion controlled nature of

The IR, NMR spectral results of products obtained after bulk electrolysis are in confirmity with the above proposed mechanism.

Methyl hydrazine exhibits absorption bands at 3240 (ν_{N-H}), 2962 (ν_{C-H} asymm.), 2872 (ν_{C-H} symm.), 1470, 1440 (δ_{C-H}), 1300, 890, 840 (δ_{N-H}) in IR spectrum and at δ 7.26 and 7.27 for NH_2 proton, at δ 2.18 for methyl proton in 1H NMR spectrum.

These spectral data are in confirmity with the reported results of methyl hydrazine¹⁷, yield 78.02% (Found : C, 25.82; H, 12.79; N, 61.70. Calcd. for $C_1H_6N_2$: C, 26.07; H, 13.04; N, 60.87%).

Aniline exhibits absorption bands at 3450 (ν_{N-H} asymm.), 3350 (ν_{N-H} symm.), 3040 (ν_{Ar-H}), 1650 (δ_{N-H}), 1640-1450 (ν_{C-C} in-plane skeletal vibrations), 1250 (ν_{C-N}), 750, 700 cm^{-1} (δ_{C-H} mono substitution) in IR spectrum and at δ 3.5 for NH_2 proton and δ 7.1 for aryl proton in 1H NMR spectrum, yield 81.45% (Found : C, 78.09; H, 7.9; N, 15.63. Calcd. for C_6H_7N : C, 77.42; H, 7.53; N, 15.05%).

In non-aqueous media :

The cyclic voltammograms of MPHT were also recorded in potential range 1800 to -500 mV at different scan rates 100, 200, 300, 400, 500 mV/s in CH_2Cl_2 (Fig. 7). The repetitive scanning revealed the presence of cathodic peak at more negative potential indicates the irreversible reduction behaviour of electron transfer process.

Fig. 7. Cyclic voltammograms of 1 mM MPHT in CH_2Cl_2 .

Effect of complexation :

The cyclic voltammograms of $Cu(MPHT)_2$ complex in the potential range from 1000 to -850 mV (vs Ag/

AgCl) at different scan rates 100, 200, 300, 400, 500 mV/s in CH_2Cl_2 solution is shown in Fig. 8. Cyclic voltammograms of complex exhibit one pair of current peaks in the range of -0.3 to +0.1 V. Since the free

Fig. 8. Cyclic voltammograms of 1 mM Cu complex of MPHT in CH_2Cl_2 .

ligand and copper(II) ion do not exhibit any current peak in this region, the observed currents peaks must be related to the metal-centre of the complex. The E_{pc} and E_{pa} values shifted in the cathodic and anodic direction respectively as scan rate increases, thus ΔE_p increases with increase in scan rate and was found to be more than 60 mV. The ratio of anodic (I_a) and cathodic (I_c) peak currents was not equal to unity. These results suggest a quasi-reversible electrode process having no coupled chemical reaction. The voltammetric data obtained from the cyclic voltammograms are summarized in Table 3. The single

Table 3. CV parameters of 1 mM MPHT and 1 mM $Cu(MPHT)_2$ in CH_2Cl_2

Compd.	Scan rate (v) (mV/s)	E_{pc} (mV)	E_{pa} (mV)	I_{pc} (μA)	I_{pa} (μA)
MPHT	100	-3	-	87	-
	200	-45	-	100	-
	300	-69	-	204	-
	400	-108	-	243	-
	500	-141	-	305	-
$Cu(MPHT)_2$	100	-330	25	644	-271
	200	-350	32	1177	-426
	300	-362	57	1464	-491
	400	-384	60	1844	-617
	500	-390	77	2276	-910

electron transfer of this redox process has been verified by comparing its current height with that of the standard ferrocene-ferrocenium couple under identical experimental conditions.

The cathodic peak potential in cyclic voltammograms of complex shifted to more negative values than that of observed in case of ligand in CH_2Cl_2 which is in further conformity with the fact of complexation process between ligand (MPHT) and Cu metal ion (Table 3).

Conclusion :

The cathodic peak potentials of MPHT are shifted to more negative values with increase in pH, scan rate and concentration of electroactive species.

The cathodic peak current which is found to increase linearly with square root of sweep rate and also with concentration of electroactive species, suggests that the overall electrode process is diffusion controlled and irreversible.

The Cu complex of MPHT shows a simple one electron transfer, quasi-reversible electrode process.

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